

**MOTORBIKE ACCIDENTS REPORTED IN TERTIARY
CARE HOSPITALS****Dr. Nabeeha Azhar¹, Dr. Adnan Mahmood², Dr. Nuzhat Faqir Hussain³**¹ Rawalpindi Medical University² Services Hospital, Lahore³ Avicenna Medical College Lahore**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Traveling on a motorcycle carries a much higher risk of death or injury than driving the same distance in a car. This cross-sectional study was conducted in different tertiary care hospitals. The data was collected from the emergency department of these hospitals. The data of two months was collected. The data of three hundred and sixty patients was collected. In ninety percent of the patients the driver of the vehicle was injured and in sixty six percent of the case, the person sitting with the driver was injured. Among 360 patients presented with this history, 86% were male and 14% were females. Motorbike accidents can give rise to bone injuries of any body part, however, it has been determined in the study that lower limbs' bones are particularly more prone to injury in motorbike accidents.

Keywords: *Motorcycle, trauma***Corresponding author:****Dr. Nabeeha Azhar,**
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INTRODUCTION:

Traveling on a motorcycle carries a much higher risk of death or injury than driving the same distance in a car. In 2006 US motorcyclists had a risk of a fatal crash that was 35 times greater than that of passenger cars, based on 390 motorcyclist deaths per billion vehicle miles and 11.1 car fatalities for that distance. In 2016 this rate was 28 times that for automobiles.

When looking at all reported accidents regardless of injuries, the accident rate for motorcycles in the US in 2016 was 6.31 per million miles driven, significantly higher than the rate of 3.28 accidents per million miles driven for cars and similar vehicles. However the primary reason for the higher rates of injuries and fatalities among motorcyclists is that cars provide more effective crash protection. For automobiles, 31% of crashes result in injury but only 0.29% of accidents are fatal. For motorcycles 78.3% of reported crashes result in injury and 4.24% of crashes are fatal.

Statistics from other countries confirm the US data. The UK Department for Transport indicated that motorcycles have 16 times the rate of serious injuries, people either killed or injured, compared to cars. UK data for casualties, i.e. the total of all injuries and fatalities combined, showed 6,043 casualties per billion miles traveled on motorcycles in 2017, 25.4 times the rate of 238 per billion miles travelled for cars. In the UK in 2017 there were 116.9 motorcyclist fatalities per billion passenger miles, 61.5 times the rate of 1.9 fatalities per billion passenger miles for occupants of cars. UK data shows a wider disparity between cars and motorcycles than US data in part because it is based on fatalities per passenger mile while US data is based on fatalities per vehicle mile (1,2,3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in different tertiary care hospitals. The data was collected from the emergency department of these hospitals. The data of two months was collected. The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 25.0. The qualitative data was presented as frequency and percentages. The quantitative data was presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The data of three hundred and sixty patients was collected. All these patients presented with the history of motorbike trauma. In ninety percent of the patients the driver of the vehicle was injured and in sixty six percent of the case, the person sitting with the driver was injured. Eleven percent of all the patients were received in serious condition and 6% were of head injury. Rest of the patients were of mild to moderate injuries. Among 360 patients presented

with this history, 86% were male and 14% were females.

DISCUSSION:

Motorbike accidents can give rise to bone injuries of any body part, however, it has been determined in the study that lower limbs' bones are particularly more prone to injury in motorbike accidents. In other studies from developing countries where motorbike is an important mean of traveling, tibia fracture has been reported most commonly as a result of road traffic accidents of motorbike rider.

Head injuries are the most common injuries related to motor bike injuries. Road traffic accident is considered as "silent epidemic" of the industrialized world. Traumatic brain injuries are the hallmark of road traffic accidents specially related to motor bikers those who are non-helmeted. Loss of consciousness and amnesia after trauma are the two main markers of severity of brain injury (4,5).

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